

Forced Migration, Psychological Trauma and Affective Solidarity in *A Land of Permanent Goodbyes* by Atia Abawi

Rana Kashif Shakeel

PhD Scholar, Department of English, Air University, Islamabad, Pakistan
rkshakeel820@gmail.com (Corresponding author)

Dr. Munawar Iqbal Ahmad

Professor of English, Dean Faculty of Social Sciences, Air University, Islamabad, Pakistan
munawargondal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: Refugee sufferings ensued by war experiences hang over the disciplines of pain, trauma, and refugee studies. Refugee crises caused by war, civil massacres, terrorist activities, and genocides have become a drastic issue since 1945, hence assuming more catastrophic state in contemporary times. Like other refugee nations, Syria has also been under the clouds of oppression, atrocity and insurgency since March 2011 when civil war erupted all around Syria. The victims were forced to flee their homeland to save their lives. Fleeing from insurgencies prevailing in Syria brought about refugee trauma to the Syrians, that can be divided into three phases—‘pre-displacement’, ‘displacement’ and ‘post-displacement’. The issue grabbed the attention of academicians and political intelligentsia who documented the war crimes and refugee crises, and their effects on both victims and witnesses. As a common trend, the existing scholarship focused majorly on the bleak sides of the refugee crises and refugee trauma, whereas disregarded the elements of resilience, intra-communal and inter-community solidarity. So, contributing to the existing scholarship, the present research focuses on analyzing the Syrian novel *A land of permanent goodbyes*, through eclectic theoretical framework based on the theories of trauma theorists Cathy Caruth (1996) and Dori Laub (1992), and solidarity theorists Carol C. Gould (2007) and Paul de Beer & Ferry Koster (2009). By analysing the representative excerpts of the novel, the study aims to explore the interconnections among forced displacement and ‘trauma studies’. It also investigates how the social injustice stimulates the past trauma events. Moreover, the study also demonstrates how refugee trauma invokes the solidarity acts. This representative study will surely be a sort of fresh critical bent for other alike research works.

Keywords: victim(S), witness(Es), refugee crisis, refugee trauma, displacement, nightmare, hallucination, solidarity

[Introduction](#)

[Literature Review](#)

[Statement of the Problem, Rationale, and Objectives of the Study](#)

[Research Methodology](#)

[Textual Analysis](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

1.1. Refugee Crises: An Overview

Refugee crises emerge from forced migration, which is also known as forced displacement (Loescher, 2021) and/or forced relocation (“Forced displacement,” 2022). An

individual is forced to migrate when the element(s) of coercion involving a threat to life and livelihood arise(s). Such threats originate from either natural or (hu)man-caused/made disasters ("Forced migrant, n.d.). Natural disasters, according to Laurence J. Kirmayer et al. (2010), refer to meteorological and geophysical catastrophic events like volcanoes, earthquakes, floods, tsunamis, tornadoes, and droughts, whereas (hu)man-caused/made disasters can be divided into 'technological accidents' and 'willful events'. Technological accidents involve mass transportation accidents, the collapse of buildings or bridges, and industrial accidents, whereas "mass murders, terrorism, war, and genocide" (p. 156) are the sub-categories of willful or intentional disasters. In the wake of both (hu)man-caused/made destructions and natural devastations, the affectees are expected to react in two quite inverse ways. They have to choose between 'fighting against the violent forces' and 'fighting away from the danger zones to safe places'. Since they are made physically, psychologically, economically, and politically so weak and helpless (Loescher, 2021), they have to choose the second option. Fleeing for their lives, they either cross the international borders of their countries or become internally displaced people (IDPs).

The refugee crisis, entailed by hu(man)-caused/made disasters or nature-made disasters, has always remained a challenging issue (Kadavan, 2021) for all humankind since the antiquities. Despite the unavailability of authentic historical facts, it is unanimously acknowledged that "the refugee production is rooted in geopolitical structure" (Keely, 1996, p. 1). In this context, research studies reveal that (in the recent past), since 1945 about fifty to sixty million people were uprooted and displaced from Europe, Africa, and Asia. The volume of the problem has become more ghastly since the 1950s. The stats provide that over one hundred million people have been forcibly displaced globally ("Refugee crisis," n.d.) as a result of (hu)man-caused/made conflicts, persecutions, violations of human rights and violence ("Global refugee statistics," 2023). In this connection, a report enlisted the ten most violence-affected countries and territories i.e. Syria, Ukraine, Afghanistan, South Sudan, Rohingya (Myanmar), Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Sudan, Somalia, Central African Republic (CAR), and Eritrea ("The 10 largest refugee crises," 2023). In addition, the other regions—Venezuela, Central Sahel, Iraq, Yemen, and Northern Ethiopia ("The most urgent refugee crises," (2021) are also the souring sites of war and violence. Analyzing the statistics, the reports reveal that violence, violation of human rights, and the subsequent refugee crises in Syria are worse than the recent crises in Ukraine and Rohingya. To strengthen the bitter truth, the latest records indicate that by the end of 2022, about 6.8 million Syrians sought refuge, primarily in the neighboring countries Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Egypt, and Turkey, but factually Turkey hosted the largest number of Syrian refugees i.e. 3.7 million (Hickson & Wilder, 2023; "Refugee statistics," n.d.).

1.2. Conflict-Induced Refuge and Trauma Studies

Psychological trauma is an emotional response to a dreadful or crucially negative event (Reyes et al., 2008; Figley, 2012). Such events are qualified by their emotionally horrifying and shocking threat to life, or violation of bodily integrity (Reyes et al., 2008, p. x). It further results in the functional and emotional decomposition of an individual (Herman, 1997; Reyes et al., 2008; Keynan, 2012). The causes of trauma may either be, as discussed earlier, the (hu)man-made/caused or nature-made/caused (Keynan, 2012). War and violence, and the resultant forced migrations or displacements are (hu)man-made/caused phenomena.

Conflict-induced displacement, in other words, forced migration, is an outcome of the war, violence, militancy, persecution, and human rights violations. Since this type of migration involves negative occurrences, the refugees who flee from combat zones of war and violence are highly susceptible to psychological trauma. In other words, the refugees, like other types of affectees, are highly vulnerable to PTSD syndromes, and other trauma-related disorders (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018). In addition to the affectees (more properly

victims), the witness (primary or secondary) of violence, fear, or imminent death, also suffers from psychological trauma (Figley, 2012; Mohacsi, 2021).

1.3. Refugee Literature: A Mode of Testimony of Trauma

Each type of trauma requires a voice to transcribe and pronounce the suffering of a victim, a bystander or a witness. A traumatized individual bears witness to an event that involves life and death issues. To a witness, it becomes a moral obligation and a psychological burden to testify to the lived experience (Figley, 2012). Shoshana Felman (1995) connects the act of testimony with the verbalizing of trauma. She asserts that testimony has become such a significant literary mode in the contemporary world, that “[the] era can precisely be defined as the age of testimony” (Felman, 1995, p. 17). It is because of the catastrophes prevailing throughout the twentieth century. James Berger (1997), in this context, writes that the two world wars, civil wars, local wars, ethnic wars, ideological wars, genocides, and other conflicts “shaped our understanding of the world” (Mohacsi, 2021, p. 7).

Literature, being a mode of trauma testimony, has grabbed the attention of first-wave trauma theorists like Shoshana Felman and Dori Laub (1995), Cathy Caruth (1996), and Judith Herman (1997). The first-wave theorists majorly focused on the testimonies of Holocaust witnesses (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018). The devastating experiences at the concentration camps and the dislocation of millions of Jews during the Holocaust (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018) have been materialized into a literary genre. Since the first-wave theorists' works on trauma theory concerning the Holocaust are considered something “like the canon of trauma theory” (Minczingerová, 2009, p. 6), the Holocaust was also modeled to be an unparalleled trauma in global history. But later on the theorists like Michael Rothberg in his book *Multidirectional memory*, Stef Craps in his book *Postcolonial witnessing: Trauma out of bounds* (2012), and Sonya Andermahr in her book *Decolonizing trauma studies: Trauma and Postcolonialism* (2018) arguably recommended that the traumas beyond the Holocaust should be considered for discussion, research, and theorization. In this respect, Stef Craps suggested to engage a “more inclusive trauma theory” (Craps, 2013, p. 51) for scholarly endeavours. In other words, colonial experiences, territorial partitions, civil wars, genocides, and the resultant forced migrations around the world should also be given earnestly due attention and representation.

1.4. Syrian Civil War Violence and A Land of Permanent Goodbyes

The bitter experiences related to refugee trauma are represented in refugee literature, which is the sub-discipline of war trauma literature. Although there is no patent definition of refugee literature, Barbara Huber (2018) provides that it include the texts that are written by, for, or about refugees. Speaking otherwise, such texts are the written testimonies by both the victims and witnesses (the details discussed earlier).

Syrian civil war broke out in 2011, which shattered the lives of the people. The stories of civil war were, first, published by the media groups who turned the story of war into just the story of bloodshed, persecution, and unending violence, the perpetual images of militancy, and the Syrian peoples' weaknesses and helplessness (Nicholls, 2020). Sensation-driven and emotion-driven retelling of such traumas lack the positive images of resilience, courage, and solidarity from inside the community or from some outsiders. Such trauma stories, deficit of positivity, are the fashion of the day not only in the case of Syria but also with other similar traumas. Therefore, it can be posited that the reporters, as secondary witnesses, become one of the major causes of the crisis of the authenticity of testimony. So, a partial approach to refugee literature as the Kaleidoscopes of only war-trodden images has been remonstrated by Nicholls (2020).

Syria, the most persecuted combat zone, and the Syrian civilians crushed by the militancy of ISIS (Daesh) and the governmental army of Bashar-al-Assad—both have been

depicted appropriately in Atia Abawi's famous novel *A land of permanent goodbyes*. The choice of this novel is quite appropriate because it presents not only the traumatic plight of the refugees at both the individual and the collective levels but also displays how trauma becomes a driving force for solidarity acts within the community and beyond the community.

1.4.1. A Brief Summary of *A Land of Permanent Goodbyes*

The story revolves around the teenage protagonist Tareq who is spending a happy life with his parents Nour and Fayed; his grandmother *Teyta*; his siblings Salim, Farrah, Susan, Ameer and Sameer. Although their domestic life is full of happiness, the prevailing militancy and the sites of destruction in the city have made Tareq susceptible to the fear of losing his family, especially his mother. All these fears are frequently reflected through his nightmares. Soon, the nightmares are materialized into reality when a bomb hits their home, killing all the members of his family except his father, and a younger sister Susan. From the debris of his devastated house, and the hospital, they recover the dead bodies of their loved ones except the dead body of Salim. After this painful incident, they decide to leave their country for good. On their way, they have to face insult and atrocity at the hands of the soldiers and militants appointed at the checkpoints. Finally, they cross the international borders and reach Turkey. From Turkey, they want to cross the sea to reach Greece from where they would cross the international borders of Germany. Due to financial restrictions, his father remains in Turkey, whereas, Tareq along with Susan get ready to cross the sea under the supervision of some human traffickers. All the refugees including Tareq and Susan are loaded in inflatable dinghies like non-humans. Even, on their voyage from Aleppo to Greece, some of the passengers breathe their last. At the seashore of Greece, there are many volunteers whose solidarity acts give a new life to the conflict-induced refugees.

2. Literature Review

A land of permanent goodbyes prefaces the existing turmoil of the Syrian civil war, in which the governmental power agencies working for Bashar-al-Assad, the militants of Daesh/ISIS, and the others were involved. The prevalent situation forced the people to flee Syria with the hope of "finding safety in Europe" ("A land of permanent goodbyes," 2018). The novel shares the similar themes i.e. of war and refugee trauma with certain other literary works. It has a very close affinity with the Syrian refugee novels *Escape from Aleppo* by S.N. Senzai (2018), *The map of salt and stars* by Zeyn Joukhadar (2018), and *The beekeepers of Aleppo* by Christy Lefteri (2020). The main characters of *Escape*: Nadia; *Salt and stars*: Nour; and *The beekeepers*: Nuri—all try to escape from the Syrian civil war, which traumatizes them in one or the other way (Nicholls, 2020). In these novels, fleeing the homeland is the only practical step to life. In *Goodbyes*, the troublesome journey from Syria to Turkey, the dreadful voyage from Turkey to Greece, and then insecure attempts of border crossing to Germany are the only forcible practical steps to "survival...evading persecution and probable death" (Bunn, 2017, p. 103).

Refugee sufferings associated with war experiences lie at the crossroads of pain, susceptibility, and trauma studies. Refugees have to undergo a series of discomforts ranging "from mental disorders to somatic pain" (Hron, 2018, p. 288), and a variety of social injustice(s), economic and political discrimination(s), which bring about violence, poverty, isolation and alienation to the lives of the refugees. Hron (2018) aligns this type of refugee distress with the concept of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) which came to the scene "with the survivors of the Holocaust ... [and] Vietnam [war]" (Fernando, 2021, p. 30), and was recognized by American Psychologists Association (APA) in the 1980s (Ringel, 2011). Briefly, PTSD entails "abusive memories, nightmares or flashbacks" (Hron, 2018, p. 288). The PTSD symptoms become hyperactive as soon as some current problem occurs on the way to refuge. In his research titled "Struggle between Resilience vs Trauma in the

novel,” Fernando (2021) engages the Freudian concepts of stimuli. It is further stated that the stimuli can be as simple as some object, person, place, event, or “even a sound of a bullet in war” (p. 31). This instinct of “compulsion to repeat” (p. 31) creates a psychological tension, which sets aside pleasure (Freud’s *Beyond the pleasure principle*, 1961; quoted in Fernando, 2012). After providing a detailed account of the Freudian concept, Fernando (2012) applies these theoretical concepts to different characters of *Goodbyes*. For example, the repetitive hallucination of Salim during the agonizing times of migration shows how Tareq’s mind is filled “with the past experiences that he had with his brother” (p. 33). In the same way, the exploitative dealings and indifferent behavior of the people in Turkey with Tareq also trigger back to the pleasant memories of his homeland.

Traumatic memories are not simply episodic memories because flashbacks and dreams intrude on them and turn them into fragments, hence “disturbing the cohesiveness of the self” (Lampe et al., 2011, p. 173) on the one side, and on the other side the bodily integrity of an individual (Reyes et al., 2008). It is all because the distressed person, either a victim or a witness suffers due to “certain scenes that continuously flash through his/her mind” (Fernando, 2021, p. 30). In Fernando (2021) and Ahmad et al. (2023), with minor theoretical differences, the same themes of flashbacks, hallucinations, and nightmares have been discussed. Fernando’s (2021) discussion is based on purely the ideas of Freud, and he has strived to apply them on a reasonable number of scenes of *Goodbyes*. On the other hand, Ahmad et al. (2023) have built the theoretical framework on the ideas of Freud and Caruth, but the research does not engage sufficient textual references for the validation of theoretical claims.

The major focus of Ahmad et al.’s (2023) study is to explore the reenactment of trauma. A similar aspect is provided by Fernando (2021), but with the engagement of the term ‘stimuli/stimulus’ provided by Freud. Ahmad et al. (2023) relate reenactment with Caruthian sub-categories of ‘known’ and ‘not-known’ war trauma. In the introductory part of the research paper, Ahmad et al. (2023) also establish that the research is concluded with a novel paradigm that portrays trauma as a healer rather than a mere wound. By doing so, the research seems to be aligning itself with Nicholls’ (2020) critique cum opinion-based ideals that instead of propagating the negative side of war, the positive side of characters displaying their integrity, valour, identity, and concept of home should be recontextualized. Although the theoretical ideas of ‘double wound’ entailing ‘known’ and ‘not-known’ have been applied to the novel, it still seems to lack the clarity of theoretical threads. It is perhaps due to the fact that Caruth herself has not elaborated well most of the terminology she uses in her works, and on which she establishes further theories.

3. Statement of the Problem, Rationale, and Objectives of the Study

The concise overview of the global refugee crises, the interrelation between the refugee crises and war, and their connection with trauma studies have been comprehensively presented to contextualize the present study. Firstly, the scarcity of available data on the subject matter demands for more investigation. Secondly, the existing research work which engaged the novel *A land of permanent goodbyes* as a source text also overlooked the resilient side of the victims’ personalities, and the solidarity acts within the trauma community, and the solidarity acts done by the people outside the trauma community. To bridge these research gaps, by engaging an eclectic theoretical framework based on the trauma theories of Cathy Caruth (1996) and Dori Laub (1992), and the solidarity theories of Carol C. Gould (2007), and Paul de Beer & Ferry Koster (2009), the present research aims at exploring the links among forced displacement and trauma studies. It also explores how the problems and social injustice stimulate the past trauma events. Moreover, the research also displays how refugee trauma becomes a vehicle for solidarity acts.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Trauma and Solidarity: An Eclectic Theoretical Approach

4.1.1. Trauma: An Indelible Psychic Scar

The term 'trauma' may be positioned verily in different contexts. Standing on the verge of interdisciplinarity, and identified by its subtleties, trauma is pondered over as an 'experience' or 'event', as well as the resultant emotional injury, psychic stress, or long-term psychological consequences. Etymologically originated from the Greek word 'traumatikos' (Garland, 2007; Groenewald, 2018; Hoad, 1996, p. 502; Muhammad & Al-Banna, 2015), and the Latin word 'traumaticus' (Hoad, 1996, p. 502), trauma primarily implied to a bodily 'wound', or 'piercing in one's skin' which could damage the bodily envelope (Fletcher, 2013; Garland, 2007). Later on, its focus was shifted from 'physical injury' to the emotional ambits of an individual (Aamir, 2020; Groenewald, 2018). This conceptual transition from 'physical' to 'emotional' spheres owes much to the theoretical contributions of Sigmund Freud (1920) who used the concept of trauma to express that the mind too can be pierced and wounded by the events (Garland, 2007, p. 9), which "overwhelm the ordinary adaptations to life" (Herman, 2015, p. 33). Explaining this phenomenon, Geoffrey Hartman (1995) took an advanced pace by positing that traumatic events are "registered [in psyche] rather than experienced" (p. 537). In Aamir's (2020) conceptualization, traumatic events are so intensely penetrating that they are naturalized into the human psyche.

The term 'trauma theory', for the first time, appeared with the publication of Cathy Caruth's monograph *Unclaimed Experience* (1996). In addition to Caruth, the works of Shoshana Felman and Dori Laub also prevailed it throughout the social sciences and humanities. Caruth, being an ardent follower of Freud extended and modified the theoretical ideas of Freud, especially those which were theorized in his book *Beyond the pleasure principle*. Caruth defines trauma as "a wound inflicted not upon the body but upon the mind" (p. 3). Advancing Freudian concepts of trauma, she also maintains that the bodily wounds are easily healable whereas the "breach in the mind's experience of time, self, and world..." (p. 4) is everlasting. From this, it can easily be deciphered that trauma is a psychic infliction.

4.1.2. The Unassimilated Nature of Trauma and Temporal Crisis

Caruth also views that trauma is not merely locatable in the simple violent or original event i.e. it is not the story of suffering or pain, rather it accounts for how it keeps an unassimilated nature. The unassimilated nature further refers to "the way it was precisely [not-known] in the first instance" (p. 4). It is because, at the time of the occurrence, the emotional shock makes victims unconscious to the situation. In this regard, she quotes the notion of 'temporal crisis' (p. 114) by Carol Jacobs. Dori Laub (1992) also endorses the idea of 'temporal crisis' by providing that "massive trauma precludes its registration, [whereas] the observing and recording mechanisms of the human mind are temporarily knocked out" (p. 57). He further points out that in such circumstances the 'known' trauma does not deemed to be fully witnessed by the victim. However, despite these objections raised by Laub, time is much more important for the narrators/witnesses/victims than the subject matter. In another way, trauma, according to Caruth (referring to Freud), is a story of a crying wound that "addresses us in the attempt to tell us of the reality or truth that is not otherwise available" (Caruth, 1996, p. 4). This truth is further associated with belatedness, which also reciprocates with 'unassimilated nature' and 'temporal crisis'.

4.1.3. Belatedness and Repetitive Nature of Trauma

Trauma is also recounted as "the response to an unexpected or overwhelming violent event or events" (p. 91). Their intensity hinders the person's consciousness to

handle and digest the situation thoroughly. However, it should not be misunderstood that the wound of the mind is healed. Influenced by the elements of 'temporal' crisis, it returns "later in repeated flashbacks, nightmares, and other repetitive phenomena" (p. 93). Traumatic experience, beyond the psychological dimension of suffering, suggests a certain paradox: that the most direct seeing of a violent event may occur as an absolute inability to know it; that immediacy, paradoxically, may take the form of belatedness. The repetitions of the traumatic event—which remain unavailable to consciousness, yet intrude repeatedly, suggest a larger relation to the event that extends beyond what can simply be seen or what can be known, and is inextricably tied up with the belatedness and incomprehensibility that remain at the heart of this repetitive seeing.

4.1.4. Trauma Witnessing and Affective Solidarity

Trauma witness is accompanied by the concept of witness. Although Laub does not give much importance to being carried away by the story of a victim, however, naturally, the listener becomes a participant and co-owner of trauma by listening to it. The listener, as a secondary or tertiary witness, "comes to partially experience trauma in himself" (Laub, 1992, p. 57). As a participant in such (an absent) event, the listener also feels and shares the victim's injury, bewilderment, conflict, and dread. With regard to this, on the one side, the listener is facing the Aristotelian state of probability, but on the other hand shares the trauma emotions of the victim.

Sharing the emotions of a victim is correlated with *affective solidarity*. It is identified by "[the] feelings of affection, responsibility or duty towards another person" (de Beer & Koster, 2009, p. 23), and *'mitgefuh'* translated as "fellow feeling" (Gould, 2007, p. 152). Committed with such fraternity based phenomena, solidarity, on the one side demands purification of the self from ego, and on the other hand, it does not anticipate any reciprocally returning reward. In Gould's (2007) conception, solidarity is not induced by any type of self-interest rather it is upheld by moral duty, sympathy or commitment. In this connection, de Beer and Koster (2009) establishes that *affective solidarity* encompasses "[the] values like altruism, charity, benevolence, and community spirit" (p. 23). In this regard, Sandra Bartkey "stresses the role of imagination as a basis for the situation of feelings and situation of the other" (quoted in Gould, 2007, p. 152). It is further related that *affective solidarity* displays that "one need not presuppose that one has already experiences those feelings oneself" (p. 152).

4.2. Analytical Framework and Delimitations

For textual analysis, certain representative situations narrated in *Goodbyes* have been engaged. The analysis takes into consideration two phases of refugee trauma i.e. 'pre-displacement' phase and 'displacement' phase (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018). At some situations, the 'post-displacement' phase has also been slightly touched upon to explore the links among situations and theoretical concepts. The eclectic theoretical framework for the research is primarily established on the theoretical strands provided by the trauma theorists Cathy Caruth (1996) and Dori Laub (1992), and the solidarity theorists Carol C. Gould (2007), and Paul de Beer and Ferry Koster (2009). Each situation has been analyzed through the lens of trauma theories, followed by the application of solidarity theories. In addition to the principal theorists, other theorists have also been taken up for further clarification.

5. Textual Analysis

The story of *A land of permanent goodbyes* begins with the images of routine domestic and social life even in the wake of Syrian Civil war. The protagonist of the novel Tareq is the witness of the prevailing militancy in Syria. This militancy makes Tareq

susceptible to the fear of losing his own loved ones. This psychological situation, in Fernando's (2021) words, is due to the terrible scenes, which cross through the minds of victims or witnesses. The atrocities faced or witnessed by Tareq of *Goodbyes* and thousands of Syrians, which produce perpetual fears, induce the affectees to migrate to the safe havens. These forcibly displaced people are the carriers of trauma within their homeland, and beyond it. This is in fact reflected through certain psychological disorders (Hron, 2018) in the refugees and the other victims of war crimes. Trauma and the psychological disorders associated with forced migration can be divided into three phases which have been described by (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018) as:

First is the pre-displacement, the home that is violently assaulted: next is the displacement phase where the refugee will flee their country and the journey towards safe haven can itself provide the refugee with traumatic experiences. Lastly is the post-displacement phase, the experience of now living in a new country as a refugee, a status often pervaded with feelings of non-belonging (p. 14).

5.1. Trauma During 'Pre-displacement' Phase

The first phase of trauma (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018) is prevailing throughout the novel *Goodbye* as its narration is saturated with ongoing process of nightmares and shell-shocks. The 'pre-displacement' phase of trauma preludes to the 'displacement' phase. The existing turmoil of civil war caused by the power agencies of Syria—the army of Bashar-al-Assad, Daesh/ISIS, and the others have left indelible marks on the personhood of the victims, because the mind is highly vulnerable to be wounded by the events (Garland, 2007). The violent circumstances and the psychic wounds enroot fear in Tareq's personhood. He is always afraid of being separated from his family, especially from his mother. The fear has lodged itself in his self after he has witnessed the indiscriminate bombing scenes on the TV. In Caruthian terms, the trauma of Tareq at this stage is not linked with his own trauma, rather it is "tied with [another's] trauma" (Caruth, 1996, p. 8). Similarly, applying Laub's terminology, Tareq becomes the co-owner of trauma of the others (Laub, 1992). So, it is related with listening to the others wounds i.e. in the capacity of a secondary witness (Laub, 1995). Resultantly, his nightmares, installed in his psyche (Aamir, 2020; Hartman, 1995), are full of the images of intense bombing. In the beginning of chapter 2 while sleeping, during his nightmare, he sees the death of his mother. Out of fear, he calls his mother repeatedly, but is unable to hear his mother even if she shouts back. Such nightmares, in actual, are provoked by the real life oppression. It, in other words, is an unconscious remembering of a traumatic event that remains buried in the victims (Caruth, 1996) like Tareq. Moreover, in the nightmare, he also sees "his vibrating body camouflaged in the rubble; the dust from the bombed-out apartment building" (Abawi, 2018, p. 11). He is filled with terror as he has already witnessed such prevailing destructions "in the movies or on television newscasts—and in his worst nightmares" (p. 11). Here, the concept of temporal crises theorized by Caruth (1996) and Laub (1992) are very relevant, because witnessing trauma knocks out the observing and recording mechanisms. After waking up, he returns to the world of reality and realizes that it was another nightmare. Happiness on discovering his mother alive is once again contaminated by the fear of loss. In the story, "when he [sees] the back of her head, hair in a bun and mole on the side of the neck, he [runs] to his mother ... tight[ly] embrace[s] ... kiss[es] her shoulder" (p. 12) but the happiness is soon faded away by "the rubble from his dream flash[ing] in his mind" p. 2). At another place, the television report of bombing that destroyed a whole family "including many children" (p. 17) triggers nightmares. Here nightmares stand for a stimulus described by Freud. The presence of a stimulus is actually the absence of happiness. The nightmare is suddenly materialized into reality, changing the position of Tareq from secondary witness

to the primary witness. A bomb hits their home, and all the family members except his father Fayed and his sister Susan, are killed.

This devastating incident is also accompanied by the images of solidarity. First phase of trauma i.e. 'pre-displacement' phase becomes a vehicle for intra-communal solidarity that means, "a shared sense of doing good" (Mason, 2000, p. 2) and a moral obligation (Rorty, 1993) beyond the family bounds, to the fellow citizens (Pensky, 2008). These basic concepts of solidarity are highly applicable to the story of *Goodbyes*. After bombing, Tareq is rescued by two white helmet men. Here we find the intra-communal solidarity dovetailed with *affective solidarity*. Sharing the feelings of a victim (de Beer & Koster, 2009) is reflected in the novel, through the personae of the men with "a thick layer of death and broken souls" (p. 21), wearing the same uniforms and helmets stained with the gloom of war. The rescuers, being the secondary witness also avoid the trauma of the others. For example, one of the rescuers named Ahmad hands over the dead body of Farrah to Tareq, and quickly turns and moves away to avoid the grief. As a witness to the trauma, "his only way to cope was to keep working and continue digging" (p. 21). This noble cause of helping his fellow Syrians, according to Gould's (2007) theories is a selfless action, which was initiated when "the war broke out" (Abawi, 2018, p. 22). *Affective solidarity* is seen through the actions of altruism, benevolence and the sense of community spirit (de Beer & Koster, 2009) displayed through the characters of Ahmad in the 'pre-displacement' phase, and Alexia and Annis in the 'displacement' phase. Its theoretical evidence in the novel is at the situation where Ahmad decides to join Syrian Civil Defense at the cost of leaving his studies, and abandoning his plans.

Solidarity also accompanies both trauma witnessing and fear. Out of fear, his mother "beg[s] him to stop his work" (p. 22) but he responds her that if he does not help his people, he will be no less than a living dead. This can be further substantiated by Sandra Bartkey's theorization where she provides that imagination plays a vital role in such contexts, as the solidary person feels himself in the shoes of the victims.

5.2. Trauma During 'Displacement' Phase

During civil war, the choice between life and death is actually a decision making whether the victims should fight or flight. Either of the two decisions manufactures trauma that indeed stands for the trauma during 'displacement' phase (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018). It is prompted by the first phase of trauma i.e. 'pre-displacement', because the circumstances improvised by the coercive powers cause forced dislocation of the war trodden victims. In the *Goodbyes*, after the "[bomb] strike that killed [Tareq's] family," (Abawi, 2018, p. 30), Fayed, the father of Tareq, decides to migrate to some safe sanctuary. The decision made by Fayed is justified (Fernando, 2021) because he wants to save his children. The fear of loss is further reinvigorated by the 'traumatic neurosis' and 'shell-shock' with which he confronts repeatedly. Additionally, the decision of fleeing is powerfully provoked by the hallucinations, flashbacks and nightmares (Hron, 2018) loaded with the images of "the ghosts of his other children and wife" (p. 30) that constrict his every breath. Resultantly, refugee crises in many guises accompany them as an uninvited companion throughout their journey.

It is an undeniable fact that the struggle for survival puts everyone to trials when one strives to cross the borders to some anonymous hostland. During the journey, Tareq and other refugees have to face many problems both within Syria and beyond the borders of Syria. The problems stimulate the past traumatic events (as theorized by Freud). Trauma, in this regard, is reactivated or boosted up by any stimulus, which may be a man, a thing or a place. In this regard, as Caruth points out (with reference to Freud) that the fatal events that "seem to be entirely outside" (p. 2) the wish and control of the people overwhelm them. In other words, the situation at the time of happening is indigestible by the

victim. Here the role of 'temporal crises' (Caruth, 1996; Laub, 1992) is fully prevailing over the personhood of the victim. In the beginning of their journey, Tareq and his father have to suffer from the bullying of the regime soldiers at the check posts. Here, seeing the *shabiha*, the pro-Assad civilian militia, Tareq's spine shivers down. It is because he remembered how a university student was "abducted by two *shabiha* men" (Abawi, 2018, p. 33), and later on "her body was ... found raped and murdered" (p. 33). This moment is directly linked with the belated (Caruth, 1996) recurrence of some traumatic event, even though it has been witnessed by Tareq in the capacity of a secondary witness.

Reactivation of traumatic feelings can be observed in many other situations. First, during the journey, Tareq comes across an old woman "dressed in black from head to toe ... for one moment he [thinks] it [is] his *Teyta*" (p. 164), who was like a gluing bond among all the family members. Here, hallucination activates, and we can see how his actual identity is hid behind the "traumatic neurosis" (Caruth, 1996, p. 130). Secondly, when Susan names her doll after the name of his dead sister Farrah, Tareq is shocked chocked, and "swallows a painful serrated gulp of emotions" (Abawi, 2018, p. 40). We may link this with their past domestic life where all brothers and sisters were living under the blessed umbrella of their parents and *Teyta*. In this regard, following Caruth's ideas, we may say that in Tareq's personality "the experience of trauma repeats itself, exactly and unremittingly, through [his unknowing acts], and against his very will" (p. 2).

Traumatic experiences, as uncontrolled entities, are bound up with "belatedness ... and repetitive seeing" (Caruth, 1996, p. 92), which is further connected with hallucination, a mode of PTSD. In *Goodbyes*, at many places, Tareq undergoes hallucinatory experiences. The most important scenes are those in which he meets his dead/lost brother Salim, who was two years younger than Tareq, and was of thirteen at the time of disappearance. Since his dead body could not be recovered, the failure of recovering dead body also contributes in giving rise to hallucinations. Tareq's state, at this moment of pain, represents all the Syrian refugees who have lost their loved ones. Abawi (2018) presents this state of Tareq and the other refugees as:

They didn't find Salim's body. That often happens in war. Families are forced to suffer not only loss, but also the bleak existence of living with dark hope. These are the people I meet with broken souls, tired hearts and lost minds, clinging to the fantasy that their loved one is living in a dreamed existence (p. 28).

During the 'displacement' phase, when Tareq feels depressed and needs someone's moral support, Salim appears in the hallucination of Tareq. He stands as "the motivation factor for Tareq" (Fernando, 2021, p. 33). His apparition appears in chapters 11, 17, and 18 with forceful pieces of conversation. For example, in chapter 11, when Tareq is feeling sad and is reluctant at the time of crossing international borders of Turkey, Salim appears to dialogue with him. The conversation is highly pathetic as well as interesting. Salim's visage asks Tareq, although he couldn't save his mother and siblings, he should flee Syria to save Susan and Baba because they need Tareq more than those who have been assassinated. When Tareq says that he does not want to leave his dead family behind, Salim responds to Tareq that he [Tareq] cannot do anything for the dead. Salim further says, "[he]'d rather be near them" (Abawi, 2018, p. 79). In addition, Salim's visage also encourages him for leaving Syria by saying that it is not the time of Tareq's death. In the same way, in chapter 19, Tareq envisions Salim sitting by him, and once again directing him to take care of Susan. This hallucinatory state and wish for reconnection with Salim in the wake of 'displacement' can be seen through the following dialogues:

Tareq: "You weren't in my dream last night."
Salim: "You missed me?" [Salim's image smiled].

Tareq: "Of course I did." [Tareq's heart sank] "I always do."

Salim: "Good." [He grinned at his older brother]. "I took the night off to rest. We have a big day today."

Tareq: "Yes, we do."

Salim: "I will race you there." [He ran toward the sea, yelling back] "You get on the boat and take care of Susan, and I will swim!" (Abawi, 2018, p. 154).

After Salim's disappearance into the "sea's mist" (p. 154), Tareq's heart suddenly sinks down. The story reveals that Tareq's mind is filled with the memories of past times, which he spent with his deceased brother. It does not mean that he has gone insane at all, rather he sometimes questions his mental state, and still remains happy with it as he is able to see his dead family members this way (Fernando, 2021).

Refugee crisis, trauma and sharing the related feelings are woven artistically in the plot of *Goodbyes*. To support this argument, the traumatic story of Muzhgan, a migrant teenage girl is very relevant. Her trauma is caused by her smuggler in Turkey who had repeatedly raped her before he finally set her free. After listening to this incident as a tertiary witness, according to Caruthian concept, once again the seeds of fear about his own sister are sown in Tareq's mind. In this mental state, Tareq seems to be passing through an absent event, and feels on his own self the injury of the victim (Laub, 1992). Christian Keyser's, in this regard, maintains that "observing another person's action, pain, or affect can trigger parts of the same neural networks responsible for executing those actions and experiencing those feelings firsthand" (Keyser's quoted in Armstrong, 2017).

The act of moral corruption done with Muzhgan, on one side, presents a picture of the problems of the refugees, and the exploitative nature of the so-called saviors of humanity, but on the other side, it also leaves the everlasting scars on the personalities of the victims and the witnesses. To mug up in Caruthian conceptualization, Muzhgan receives a "wound inflicted not [only] upon [her] body but upon [her] mind" (Caruth, 1996, p. 3), which tries to tell us the reality that can be otherwise lost. After bearing the sexual assault as a refugee, she never remains the same, because as a victim she can never evade the nightmares and eventually will become numb and silent (Ahmad, 2023). Despite being sent to the facility center, she never receives counselling and remains always terrified. It is because of the "extensive breach being made in the protective shield" (Caruth, 1996, p. 61) by the sexual abuse.

Intra-communal and inter-community Solidarity, during the phase of 'displacement' cannot be ignored. Both types of solidarity, existing in *Goodbyes* is closer to *affective solidarity*. To understand, it can be viewed that trauma affects not only the victims but also the listeners and witnesses of a traumatic event, host communities and helpers. On one side, in Turkey, Tareq and his cousin are manipulated by the employers because they have no work-permits, but on the other hand, they are exploited by the human-traffickers. Both the factors contribute to the failure of solidarity. Besides this, he also observes how the refugee women are treated disgracefully. Such scenes make him think about the safety of his sister Susan. He also thanks God that his mother is not accompanying him on this troublesome journey.

The trauma of 'displacement' phase is sometimes linked with 'post-displacement' phase. The 'post-displacement' phase is characterized by identity crises, and the feeling of homelessness even when a refugee is among the host community. In *Goodbyes* Turkey has become a contact zone for the Syrian refugees, but it is not at home with them. It is all due to the feelings of non-belongingness (Isaksen & Vejling, 2018) which arises due to the trauma that damages the personal integrity of a person. In this regard, Tareq's condition can be observed as:

The longer Tareq stay[s] in Turkey, the more he long[s] for home. But he [knows] that home [is] now a myth, despite what other Syrians he [meets] in Istanbul claim[s]. What they really crave [is] the past (Abawi, 2018, p. 84).

This is not the feeling of only Tareq, rather everyone during the phase of 'displacement' in *Goodbyes* thinks the same. The establishment of a coffee shop owned by a Syrian refugee named Rami proves the truth of this social hypothesis. The café is located in the area 'Little Syria', in Istanbul. The area has been given the name 'Little Syria' because a huge population of Syrian refugees are sheltered here. Rami views that there is no home for Syrians that is why he has made that café a home for all Syrians. In that café, the Syrian can gather and share their griefs, and trauma stories with each other. This thing refers to the intra-communal sense of recognition and solidarity. By doing so, he wants to facilitate his fellow beings just to console their traumatized selves. However, in response to this, he does not crave for any reward. Selflessness on the part of Rami identifies with the *affective solidarity* theorized by de Beer and Koster (2009). Rami's acts of *affective solidarity* are connected with his own trauma of losing his own family. Rami does not tell his traumatic story by himself, rather Shayma, a worker at the café, describes that most of the members of Rami's family were killed in the Hama Massacre thirty years ago. He is the only survivor because his mother smuggled him. Moreover, she tells that his mother was raped by the bloody soldiers of Hafez al-Assad.

With the sole purpose of sharing each other's griefs and extending solidarity towards each other, they arrange a 'get together party' at the café. Here the scenes are replete with *affective solidarity*, which entails the feelings of benevolence and community spirit (de Beer & Koster, 2009). The main purpose of the party is to "share [their] art, share [their] heart" (Abawi, 2018, p. 89). In the party, each participant's story or poetry brings Tareq back to his lost world. The shared feelings of community—the traumas of 'pre-displacement' phase, and 'displacement' phase have been rhymed by Shayma in a very forceful manner. The title of her poem "Goodbye Syria, please forgive us" (p. 90), as a stimulus (Freudian conception) triggers the past trauma of everyone, because "it [is] the pain of nation, not just an individual" (p. 92). Refugee Trauma mixed with solidarity, in Shayma's poetry is as:

"Goodbye, Home—never leave us/ We didn't want to go . . ."/ ... "We saw the people run,/ so we ran too/ ... We saw our loved ones die; we didn't want to die too."/ ... "The bombs kept dropping,/ And we kept falling,/ The guns kept firing,/ And we kept falling." ... "Our rivers went from blue to red, drop by drop/ Our dirt from brown to black, drop by drop/ Our great nation fell, city by city, town by town,/ So we left . . . following the trail of blood and tears (pp. 90-91).

Inter-community solidarity imbued with benevolence, charity and altruism (de Beer & Koster, 2009) in the wake of refugee trauma is well seen in *Goodbyes*. The major character representing all these virtues is Alexia who herself belongs to a Jewish family, but for the sake of refugees she decides to abandon her study career, as Ahmad, the Civil Defense Rescuer presented in Chapter 3 does just to "help his fellow Syrians" (p. 22). Linking it with trauma theory, we find that trauma affects not only the victims but also the listeners and witnesses of a traumatic event, host communities and helpers. Alexia portrayed by Abawi also shows traumatic symptoms when she listens to the traumatic stories of the refugees. The following statement from the novel shows how others trauma has filled Alexia with fear for her own life.

Alexia watch[es] the refugees as they [have] slept on the sides of roads ... They [are] elderly, infants, sick, healthy, wives, husbands, lovers, parents, sons and

daughters ... thousands of courageous souls ... scattered like the pebbles that [line] the shores. Most [are] grateful to be alive; others [mourn] the loved ones (Abawi, 2018, p. 109).

6. Conclusion

Abawi's narrative in *A land of permanent goodbyes* is a unique and complete picture of human suffering since the times of the eruption of Syrian civil war. The novel, like many other novels focusses on the problems of the refugees and the resultant trauma faced by the war trodden as well as the displaced victims of war. The above-discussed scenes are the epitomized examples of the psychological disorders of the victims. The story does not provide just the pathetic plight of the refugees; it showcases how the trauma of 'pre-displacement' phase is ignited by the refugee crises during the 'displacement' phase. Moreover, Abawi does not want to show only the predicament of the refugee lives but she also displays how the *affective solidarity* can jump in the traumatized world of the victims. In addition, the trauma-filled scenes are followed by the intra-communal and inter-community solidarity acts.

References

1. *A land of permanent goodbyes*. (2018). Worlds of Words. Retrieved April 18, 2023, from <https://wowlit.org/on-line-publications/review/volume-x-issue-4/9/>
2. Aamir, M. (2020). *Trauma and dislocation: A critique of selected fiction by contemporary Arab diasporic authors* [M.Phil. thesis]. <http://norr.numl.edu.pk/repository/filedownload/1290>
3. Abawi, A. (2018). *A land of permanent goodbyes*. Penguin.
4. Ahmad, M. S. (2023). No safe place for war survivors: War memory, event exposure, and migrants' psychological trauma. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2022.966556/full>
5. Andermahr, S. (2018). *Decolonizing trauma studies: Trauma and Postcolonialism*. MDPI.
6. Armstrong, K. (2017). 'I feel your pain': The neuroscience of empathy. Association for Psychological Science - APS. Retrieved December 5, 2023, from <https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/neuroscience-empathy>
7. Berger, J. (1997). Trauma and Literary theory. *Contemporary Literature*, 38(3), 569-582. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1208980>
8. Bunn, B. (2017, December). The book review: Young adults. *School Library Journal*. www.slj.com
9. Caruth, C. (1996). *Unclaimed experience: Trauma, narrative, and history*. JHU.
10. Fernando, F. A. (2021, June 1). Struggle between resilience vs trauma in the novel, *A land of permanent goodbyes*. *Boslit Journal of Language and Literature*, 1(1), 29-40. <https://dbcyelagiri.edu.in/dbcy-bjll/support/pdf/DBCY-Journal-Fernando.pdf>
11. Craps, S. (2012). *Postcolonial witnessing: Trauma out of bounds*. Springer.
12. Craps, S. (2013). Beyond Eurocentrism: Trauma theory in the global age. In G. Buelens, S. Durrant, & R. Eaglestone (Eds.), *The future of trauma theory: Contemporary literary and cultural criticism* (pp. 45-61). Routledge.
13. de Beer, & Koster, F. (2009). Taking care of each other: Trends in social solidarity. In *Sticking together or falling apart?: Solidarity in an era of individualization and globalization* (pp. 15-39). Amsterdam University Press.
14. Felman, S., & Laub, D. (1995). *Testimony: Crises of witnessing in literature, psychoanalysis and history*. Routledge.
15. Figley, C. R. (Ed.). (2012). *Encyclopedia of trauma: An interdisciplinary guide*. SAGE.
16. Fletcher, J. (2013). Freud's hysteria: "Scenes of passionate movement". In *Freud and the scene of trauma* (pp. 11-56). Fordham University Press.
17. *Forced displacement: Refugees, internally displaced and host communities*. (2022). World Bank. Retrieved May 5, 2023, from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/forced-displacement>

18. *Forced migrant*. (n.d.). *Migration and home affairs*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/forced-migrant_en#:~:text=A%20person%20subject%20to%20a,environmental%20disasters%2C%20chemical%20or%20nuclear
19. *Global refugee statistics*. (2023). UNHCR Canada. Retrieved May 15, 2023, from <https://www.unhcr.ca/in-canada/refugee-statistics/#:~:text=100%20million%20people%20were%20forcibly,of%20people%20displaced%20across%20borders>
20. Garland, C. (2007). Thinking about trauma. In C. Garland (Ed.), *Understanding trauma: A psychoanalytical approach* (pp. 9-31). Karnac Books.
21. Gould, C. C. (2007). Transnational Solidarities. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 38(1), 148-164.
http://www.carolcgould.com/uploads/1/2/5/0/12505497/transnational_solidarities_published.pdf
22. Groenewald, A. (2018). "Trauma is suffering that remains". The contribution of trauma studies to prophetic studies. *Acta Theologica, Supp(26)*, 88-102. <https://doi.org/10.18820/23099089/actat.sup26.5>
23. Hartman, G. H. (1995). On traumatic knowledge and literary studies. *New Literary History*, 26(3), 537-563. <https://doi.org/10.1353/nlh.1995.0043>
24. Herman, J. L. (1997). *Trauma and recovery: The aftermath of violence--from domestic abuse to political terror*. Basic Books.
25. Herman, J. L. (2015). *Terror*. In *Trauma and recovery: The aftermath of violence--from domestic abuse to political terror* (pp. 33-50). Basic Books. New York.
26. Hickson, A., & Wilder, C. (2023). *Protecting Syrian refugees in Turkey from forced repatriation*. New Lines Institute. Retrieved May 16, 2023, from <https://newlinesinstitute.org/displacement-and-migration/protecting-syrian-refugees-in-turkey-from-forced-repatriation/>
27. Hoad, T. F. (Ed.). (1996). *The concise Oxford dictionary of English etymology.*, Oxford University Press.
28. Hron, M. (2018). The trauma of displacement. In J. R. Kurtz (Ed.), *Trauma and Literature* (pp. 284-298). Cambridge UP.
29. Huber, B. (2018). *The importance of refugee literature in the EFL classroom: A practical guide to the selection and the teaching of refugee literature for and about young adults* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Universitat Wien. <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/open/o:1345072>
30. Isaksen, A. T., & Vejling, T. V. (2018). *Traumatic movements: A study of refugee displacement and trauma in contemporary literature* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Aalborg University.
https://projekter.aau.dk/projekter/files/281298931/Traumatic_Movements.pdf
31. Kadavan, A. S. (2021). Journey to death: Fictionalizing the Syrian refugee crisis in Khaled Hosseini's sea prayer. *International Journal of English and Comparative Literary Studies*, 2(5), 1-11.
32. Kahawita, T. (2022, September 1). *A guide to the different types of trauma*. HealthMatch. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://healthmatch.io/ptsd/different-types-of-trauma>
33. Keely, C. B. (1996). How nation-states create and respond to refugee flows. *International Migration Review*, 30(4), 1046-1066. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2547603?seq=2>
34. Keynan, I. (2012). *Psychological war trauma and society: Like a hidden wound*. Routledge.
35. Kirmayer, L. J., Kienzler, H., Afana, A. H., & Pedersen, D. (2010). Trauma and disasters in social and cultural context. In C. Morgan & D. Bhugra (Eds.), *Principles of Social Psychiatry* (2nd ed., pp. 155-178). John Wiley & Sons.
36. Lampe, J. et al. (2011). Traumas of development in the gay male. In S. Ringel & J. R. Brandell (Eds.), *Trauma: Contemporary directions in theory, practice, and research* (pp. 171-190). SAGE Publications.

37. Laub, D. (1992). Bearing witness: The vicissitudes of listening. In S. Felman & D. Laub, *Testimony: Crises of witnessing in literature, psychoanalysis and history* (pp. 57-74). Routledge.
38. Laub, D. (1995). Truth and Testimony: The process and the struggle. In C. Caruth (Ed.), *Trauma: Explorations in memory* (pp. 61-75). JHU Press.
39. Loescher, G. (2021). *Refugees: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press.
40. Mason, A. (2000). *Community, solidarity and belonging: Levels of community and their normative significance*. Cambridge University Press.
41. Minczingerová, J. (2009). *Trauma and working through in Gayl Jones's corregidora and Joy Kogawa's obasan* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Masaryk University. <https://theses.cz/id/sr1nhm?lang=en>
42. Mohacsi, E. E. (2021). Trauma, literature, and culture. *Freeside Europe Online Academic Journal*, 12, 1-11.
43. Muhammad, S. K., & Al-Banna, E. (2015, April 28). *Trauma theory*. Academia.edu - Share research. Retrieved November 5, 2022, from https://www.academia.edu/33182937/Trauma_theory
44. Nicholls, K. (2020). Stories across borders: Recontextualization of home, identity, and trauma in contemporary stories of Syrian displacement through the novels *the map of salt and stars* by Zeyn Joukhadar, *escaping Aleppo* by Atia Abawi, and *the land of permanent Goodbyes* by N. H. Senzai. *The Macksey Journal*, 1.
45. Pensky, M. (2008). *The ends of solidarity: Discourse theory in ethics and politics*. State University of New York Press.
46. *Refugee crisis: 100 million displaced*. (n.d.). The international rescue committee (IRC). Retrieved March 18, 2023, from <https://www.rescue.org/topic/refugee-crisis-100-million-displaced>
47. *Refugee statistics*. (n.d.). USA for UNHCR: The UN refugee agency. Retrieved March 16, 2023, from <https://www.unrefugees.org/refugee-facts/statistics/>
48. Reyes, G. et al. (2008). *The Encyclopedia of psychological trauma*. John Wiley & Sons.
49. Ringel, S. (2011). Overview. In S. Ringel & J. R. Brandell (Eds.), *Trauma: Contemporary directions in theory, practice, and research* (pp. 1-12). SAGE Publications.
50. Romero, A. (2018). Book review: Dear world: A Syrian girl's story of war and plea for peace, bana alabed. *WOW Review*, 10(4), 6-7. <http://hdl.handle.net/10150/658509>
51. Rorty, R. (1993). *Contingency, Irony, and Solidarity*. Cambridge University Press.
52. Rothberg, M. (2009). *Multidirectional memory: Remembering the Holocaust in the age of decolonization*. Stanford University Press.
53. *The most urgent refugee crises around the world*. (2021, March 6). World Vision Canada | Sponsor a Child | Canadian Charity. Retrieved December 10, 2022, from <https://www.worldvision.ca/stories/refugees/refugee-crises-around-the-world>
54. *The 10 largest refugee crises to know in 2023*. (2023). Concern Worldwide. Retrieved February 19, 2023, from <https://www.concern.net/news/largest-refugee-crises>